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Causal Semantic Data Representations and Goal-Oriented Interventions: First Results

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Abstract

This deliverable presents the first technical results on causal semantic data representations and communication strategies designed to support timely, robust, and goal-oriented interventions in future 6G networks. By shifting from traditional data-centric paradigms to causality-aware, purpose-driven information flows, we investigate how semantic relevance and causal impact can guide both data representation and transmission across diverse application domains. The report covers four complementary contributions: (i) a channel state information (CSI)-free semantic estimation framework for networked control systems using innovation-based signalling and static-gain state reconstruction; (ii) a temporal integration mechanism to preserve event chronology across distributed sensors under stochastic communication delays; (iii) a trustworthy image semantic communication architecture that leverages explainable semantics and Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI)-enabled reconstruction for multi-task efficiency; and (iv) a novel learning framework for causal abstraction grounded in the Semantic Embedding Principle, enabling structured reasoning across resolution levels. Together, these results offer a cohesive and layered foundation for implementing semantic communication systems that are causally grounded, task-aligned, and computation- and communication-efficient, laying the groundwork for intelligent and resilient goal-oriented 6G applications.

Keywords

Causal semantics, semantic communication, goal-oriented interventions, networked control systems, innovation-based estimation, temporal integration, simultaneity preservation, explainable AI, image semantic communication, generative AI, semantic abstraction, structural causal models, 6G networks.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

6G	Sixth Generation
A-seg	Annotated Segmentation Map
ADMM	Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALOHA	ALOHA Access Protocol
B-seg	Boundary-aware Segmentation Map
BLEU	Bilingual Evaluation Understudy
BS	Base Station
CA	Causal Abstraction
CDF	Cumulative Distribution Function
CLIP	Contrastive Language-Image Pretraining
cobots	Collaborative Robotics
CoCa	Contrastive Captioners
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSI	Channel State Information
DFS	Deep text-image-segmentation Fusion
ES-IRM	Explainable Semantics-based Image Reconstruction Module
FastSAM	Fast Segment Anything Model
FID	Fréchet Inception Distance
GALIP	Generative Adversarial contrastive Language-Image Pretraining
GenAI	Generative Artificial Intelligence
ISC	Image Semantic Communication
IS-text	image semantic text
JSCC	Joint Source-Channel Coding
KL	Kullback-Leibler divergence
LPIPS	Learned Perceptual Image Patch Similarity
MIMO	Multiple Input Multiple Output
MMSE	Minimum Mean Square Error
NCS	Networked Control Systems
NER	Named Entity Recognition
NMSE	Normalized Mean Square Error
PDF	Probability Distribution Function
PDV	Packet Delay Variation
PG	Proximal Gradient
PSNR	Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio
PSV	Probability of Simultaneity Violation
ROI	Region of Interest
SCA	Successive Convex Approximation
SCM	Structural Causal Model
SEP	Semantic Embedding Principle
SOC	Splitting Orthogonality Constraints
SPADE	Spatially-Adaptive Denormalization
TDMA	Time Division Multiple Access
TWI	Temporal Window of Integration
YOLOv8	You Only Look Once version 8

1 Introduction

The emergence of the Sixth Generation (6G) systems calls for a fundamental shift from traditional data transmission toward a more intelligent, adaptive, and purpose-driven communication paradigm [CSL+24]. Conventional systems focus on transmitting data with high fidelity, often without considering the actual impact of that data on downstream tasks. In contrast, 6G envisions a network that is capable of interpreting, prioritizing, and acting on information based on its meaning and relevance to specific goals. Within this vision, causal semantic communication plays a central role: rather than treating all data equally, systems must identify and prioritize information that has a direct causal influence on system behaviour, decision-making, or control performance [TSX23].

Such an approach requires not only a rethinking of communication protocols, but also new principles for representation, estimation, and abstraction. Data must be encoded and interpreted in ways that reflect the underlying causal relationships within the environment or system. This implies discarding irrelevant correlations and focusing instead on those signals and representations that truly affect the evolution of the system or the success of a given task.

This deliverable directly addresses the objectives of the 6G-GOALS project by developing causal semantic representation methods that align with the goals of WP4. In particular, it emphasizes the temporal dimension of causality—where causes precede effects—as highlighted in Task 4.2, and integrates this with structural causal reasoning from Task 4.3. These representations are applied across diverse settings, including networked control systems, distributed sensing, and semantic perception. The focus is on methods that identify and extract causally relevant information, enable its efficient and robust transmission under communication constraints, and ensure that it can be directly exploited by downstream processes such as estimation, recognition, or abstraction. The approaches presented here aim to bridge low-level signal processing with high-level semantic understanding, all grounded in the principle of causal relevance.

The structure of the deliverable is as follows. Section 2 provides a unified storyline that links the different technical contributions under a common causal semantic framework. Sections 3 to 6 present the individual contributions in detail, each addressing a distinct problem domain. Section 7 concludes the deliverable and outlines future directions.

2 From Causal Semantics to Goal-Oriented Interventions

2.1 Unifying Vision

In the 6G-GOALS framework, data representation is no longer just about efficient encoding, but about causality and goal alignment. The growing complexity of cyber-physical systems and Artificial Intelligence (AI)-native communication networks demands a new paradigm—where data is valued not for its statistical properties alone, but for its causal impact on decision-making, estimation, and task performance.

This section provides a unifying narrative that aligns the diverse technical contributions presented in this deliverable around a shared objective: enabling causal semantic communication that supports timely and trustworthy goal-oriented interventions.

2.2 From Sensing to Abstraction: A Causal Perspective

The technical results in this deliverable span different layers of a causal information flow, each tackling the representation, transmission, or interpretation of causally relevant information in networked systems:

- Section 3 focuses on semantic estimation in networked control systems. It introduces an implicit communication mechanism over Multiple-Input-Multiple-Output (MIMO) fading

channels, where sensors transmit innovation signals, defined as the discrepancy between the real-time measurement and its predicted value, without requiring full channel state information (CSI). The innovation signal serves as a compressed, causally meaningful representation of sensing errors, enabling stable estimation under tight communication constraints.

- Section 4 addresses causal event ordering across distributed sensors. It tackles the challenge that wireless delays can disrupt the temporal structure of observed events. The Temporal Window of Integration (TWI) framework reconstructs causally consistent sequences across asynchronous signals, ensuring reliable multisensor perception.
- Section 5 explores visual semantic communication using generative AI. It applies causal reasoning to select semantically relevant visual elements (e.g., object segments or descriptions) for transmission based on their impact on downstream tasks. A closed feedback loop ties semantic content to task performance, aligning transmitted information with causal influence.
- Section 6 introduces causal abstraction learning. Using the Semantic Embedding Principle, it learns multiresolution representations that preserve causal dependencies across abstraction levels. This allows reasoning and intervention to be performed reliably even at coarser levels of detail.

Together, these contributions form a layered view of causal semantic processing—from raw signals and timing to semantic selection and abstract reasoning.

2.3 Common Causal Principles Across the Deliverable

Despite differences in domain and technique, all contributions in the deliverable are grounded in shared causal principles:

- **Causal Relevance over Raw Data Fidelity:** The focus is on transmitting or processing only information that influences future system behaviour or decisions, rather than all available raw signals.
- **Time-Aligned Semantics:** Especially in Sections 3 and 4, causal semantics are tightly linked to timing. Ensuring the correct causal order of data is crucial for reliable perception and interpretation.
- **Causal Feedback and Task Alignment:** In Section 5, causal feedback is implemented through task-driven semantic control, where the transmitter selects and schedules semantic content based on feedback from downstream task performance. This forms a closed-loop interaction between representation, communication, and inference, aligning transmitted semantics with causal impact on task success.
- **Structure-Preserving Abstractions:** In Section 6, causal relationships are preserved even when moving to coarser representations, enabling generalization without losing causal integrity.

These principles define the causal semantic foundation necessary for next-generation communication and learning systems.

3 Causal Semantic Data Representation for Networked Control Systems

3.1 Context and motivation

Remote state estimation is a critical function for enabling intelligent behavior in networked control systems (NCSs), especially in future 6G-GOALS scenarios involving collaborative robotics

(cobots), autonomous vehicles, and industrial automation. In such systems, distributed sensors must report state information to remote controllers under tight timing and reliability constraints. Accurate estimation of system states is essential for maintaining stability, coordinating actions, and ensuring safety.

Within the 6G-GOALS framework, remote state estimation exemplifies the transition from traditional data-centric communication to semantic and goal-oriented paradigms. Rather than transmitting raw measurements indiscriminately, the focus shifts to conveying only information that is causally relevant to the task of state reconstruction. This aligns with semantic communication principles that prioritize the meaning and impact of transmitted data, and reflects goal-oriented communication objectives where the value of a message is defined by its contribution to control and decision-making performance. However, realizing this vision in practice requires overcoming several key limitations of conventional remote estimation frameworks.

Most existing approaches operate under idealized assumptions [PLL+23], such as perfect knowledge of the channel state at the receiver and dedicated communication resources for each sensor. In practice, acquiring and maintaining accurate CSI requires continuous pilot signalling, which significantly increases communication overhead and power consumption—particularly in large-scale, resource-constrained sensor networks. Furthermore, conventional methods typically transmit raw measurements [PLL+23], leading to inefficiencies in both spectrum usage and information relevance. These limitations highlight the pressing need for more efficient communication strategies that are robust to channel uncertainties and capable of prioritizing the transmission of information that is causally relevant to the system's behaviour and control objective. That is, instead of treating all data equally, the system should emphasize the delivery of information that has a direct causal influence on the evolution or estimation of the plant state, thus enabling more meaningful and efficient semantic representations for control-centric communication.

3.2 System model and problem statement

We consider a discrete-time linear causal dynamical system observed by multiple spatially distributed wireless sensors and monitored remotely by a central estimator through a MIMO wireless fading channel, as shown in Figure 3-1. The state evolution of the physical plant is governed by a stochastic linear process:

$$x(t+1) = Ax(t) + w(t),$$

where $x(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{S \times 1}$ is the plant state at time $t \in 0, 1, 2, \dots$, $A \in \mathbb{R}^{S \times S}$ is the known system matrix, and $w(t) \sim N(0, W)$ is zero-mean Gaussian process noise. This model captures the causal dependency of future system states on their past, which is central to both prediction and control in networked systems. The system is observed by M sensors, each equipped with N_t transmission antennas, sharing wireless resources for measurement transmission. The observation model of the m -th sensor is represented by:

$$z_m(t) = C_m x(t),$$

where $C_m \in \mathbb{R}^{N_t \times S}$ captures the connection topology between the sensor and the state vector.

The sensors transmit their measurements over a shared wireless MIMO fading channel to a central estimator with N_r receive antennas via analog aggregation. The received signal at time t is modelled as:

$$y(t) = \sum_{m=1}^M \delta_m(t) H_m(t) s_m(t) + v(t),$$

where $\delta_m(t) \in \{0,1\}$ is a Bernoulli random variable modelling the random activity of sensor m , with activation probability p . $H_m(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_r \times N_t}$ is the MIMO channel gain matrix between sensor m and the estimator, capturing path loss, fading, and shadowing. $s_m(t)$ is the transmitted signal from sensor m , which will be elaborated in details in the following. $v(t) \sim N(0, I_{N_r})$ is the additive white Gaussian noise at the receiver.

The core estimation objective is to compute the Minimum Mean Square Error (MMSE) estimate of the state vector $x(t)$ based on the received signals up to time t , denoted as

$$\hat{x}(t) = E[x(t)|y(0), \dots, y(t)],$$

The central challenge lies in achieving accurate and stable estimation over wireless channels without relying on perfect CSI, which is often costly or impractical to obtain in real-time. Moreover, in the context of causal semantic data representation, not all sensor data should be treated equally; instead, emphasis should be placed on transmitting information that is causally relevant to the system's future evolution and control decisions. This motivates the need for communication-efficient strategies that extract and convey only the most causally impactful semantic content from sensor observations.

Figure 3-1 Typical architecture of a causal remote state estimation system over a wireless network

3.3 Proposed methodology and solution

To overcome the limitations of CSI-dependent estimation and the inefficiencies of raw-data transmission, we propose a causal semantic estimation framework based on two core principles:

- Transmitting only causally relevant innovations from the sensors;
- Using a CSI-free, low-complexity estimator at the receiver.

Causal Semantic Signal Extraction at Sensors:

Inspired by Kalman filtering theory, we recognize that the innovation term—i.e., the difference between the actual and predicted sensor observations—captures the new, unpredictable, and causally relevant information at each time step. Instead of transmitting full measurements, each sensor computes the following semantic signal:

$$s_m(t) = C_m x(t) - C_m \hat{x}_f(t),$$

where $\hat{x}_f(t)$ is the causal predictor of the plant state at time t , computed using system dynamics:

$$\hat{x}_f(t) = \hat{x}(t - 1).$$

This signal represents the causal innovation of sensor m , encoding only the deviation from what the estimator already knows. Since this discrepancy is typically smaller in magnitude than raw measurements, the semantic signal leads to reduced power consumption and higher communication efficiency.

Static-Gain State Estimation at the Remote State Estimator:

Instead of relying on time-varying causal Kalman gains—which require CSI and incur significant computational overhead due to repeated matrix inversions—we employ a CSI-free, low-complexity static gain matrix K to perform the causal state update:

$$\hat{x}_f(t) + Ky(t)$$

This eliminates the need for computing dynamic gain matrices and matrix inversions in real-time. The updated state estimate $\hat{x}(t)$ is then used to generate the next prediction:

$$\hat{x}_f(t + 1) = A\hat{x}(t),$$

which is fed back to the sensors for generating the next semantic signal.

To ensure stability and performance of the estimator under random sensor activity and channel fading, we derive a closed-form sufficient condition for stability using Lyapunov drift analysis. The detailed characterizations can be found in [TSK25]. The optimal static gain K can be obtained via solving an optimization problem with respect to the sufficient condition for estimation stability using offline constrained successive stochastic convex optimization method. The "common" feedback $\hat{x}_f(t + 1)$ is then used by individual sensors to generate and transmit new semantic signals $s_m(t + 1)$. Since only broadcast feedback is required, the scheme significantly reduces communication overhead and supports a scalable implementation.

3.4 Results

We consider a linear discrete-time system with a three-dimensional state vector evolving as

$$x(t + 1) = \begin{bmatrix} 1.01 & 0.05 & 0.01 \\ 0.02 & 0.98 & 0.01 \\ 0.003 & 0.002 & 0.98 \end{bmatrix} x(t) + w(t),$$

where $w(t) \sim N(0_{3 \times 1}, I_3)$ represents zero-mean process noise. The plant state is observed by a set of sensors, each equipped with a 3×3 linear observation matrix C_m . Each m -th sensor observes only one component of the state vector in an orderly manner. Observations are transmitted over independent Rayleigh fading MIMO channels $H_m(t)$ with each element drawn i.i.d. from a zero-mean Gaussian distribution scaled to have a Rayleigh parameter of 3. The SNR is set to 12.5 dB. Sensors are activated independently at each time step with a fixed probability $p_a = 0.3$, and transmit their encoded innovation signals when activated. Based on this setup, we evaluate the performance of the proposed causal semantic estimation framework against three representative baselines.

- Baseline 1: Kalman Filtering under ALOHA Access;
- Baseline 2: Kalman Filtering under Random Time Division Multiple Access (TDMA);
- Baseline 3: Kalman Filtering with Analog Aggregation and CSI.

The three baseline schemes differ in their communication strategies and access mechanisms. Baseline 1 adopts a random ALOHA access policy, where multiple sensors may transmit simultaneously, and potential collisions are resolved at the estimator. Baseline 2 avoids collisions by selecting one sensor per time slot via a random TDMA-like schedule, reducing interference but limiting sensing diversity. Baseline 3 uses analog aggregation to simultaneously superimpose raw measurements from active sensors, offering better diversity but requiring precise CSI and power control to decode the aggregated signal. In contrast, the proposed scheme departs from all three baselines in two fundamental ways: (i) it transmits innovation signals instead of raw measurements, enabling semantic compression aligned with estimation goals; and (ii) it removes the need for CSI and pilot signaling entirely, relying on a fixed static gain matrix for estimation. This leads to a CSI-free, low-complexity solution that balances efficiency and robustness under fading channels.

Figure 3-2 shows the normalized mean square error (NMSE) as a function of the number of sensors. The proposed method consistently outperforms all baselines, especially as the number of sensors increases. Unlike Baselines 1 and 2, it avoids collisions and scheduling delays. Compared to Baseline 3, it achieves better accuracy due to the elimination of CSI estimation errors and the focus on transmitting only semantically relevant innovations.

Figure 3-2 Normalized state estimation MSE versus the number of sensors.

Figure 3-3 illustrates the total transmission power over time. Our method achieves at least 40.4% reduction in transmission power compared to CSI-dependent methods. This improvement comes from two factors: (i) the causal semantic signal being smaller in magnitude than raw measurements, and (ii) the elimination of pilot signal transmissions.

Figure 3-4 compares the total CPU time required over 10^4 time slots as the plant dimension S increases. The computation time was measured on a machine equipped with an Intel Core i7-6700 CPU, running Matlab 2024a. Each method was executed in single-threaded mode, and total CPU time was averaged over 10 Monte Carlo runs of 10^4 time slots each, excluding I/O and plotting time. The proposed static-gain estimator leads to 23.9% lower computation time compared to standard Kalman filtering, owing to the removal of real-time matrix inversions and gain updates.

3.5 Conclusions

In this work, we presented a novel causal semantic framework for remote state estimation over wireless MIMO fading channels. Motivated by the limitations of traditional Kalman-based estimators—particularly their reliance on perfect CSI and raw data transmission—we proposed a method that emphasizes the transmission of causally relevant information. Specifically, we designed a semantic signal extraction process at sensors that focuses on innovations, i.e., the

unpredictable and decision-influencing components of measurements. These innovation signals are transmitted using analog aggregation, enabling a CSI-free update of the state estimate at the receiver.

A key feature of this approach is that it preserves the causal structure of information in the sense that each transmitted semantic unit contributes directly to the estimation and future evolution of the system state. This aligns with the emerging paradigm of goal-oriented and causality-aware semantic communication in 6G networks. Furthermore, the use of a fixed linear gain—optimized offline through Lyapunov-based analysis—allows for real-time implementation with reduced computational burden.

Figure 3-3 Total transmission power at sensors versus timeslot.

Figure 3-4 Total CPU computational time versus plant dimension.

Simulation results confirm that the proposed method achieves lower estimation error, reduced sensor power consumption, and significantly lower computational complexity compared to CSI-based baselines. These findings highlight the potential of causal semantic representations as a foundation for future networked control systems that are robust, efficient, and aligned with control objectives. In addition, this work is also connected to the timing framework for semantic

communications developed in Deliverable D4. [6GGOALS-D42], as the causal innovation-based signalling naturally encodes what to transmit in real-time.

4 Time Window Integration for Simultaneity and Causality

4.1 Context and motivation

Multi-sensor fusion is essential for reliable event perception in cyber-physical systems. Furthermore, the evolution of edge computing and AI technologies is creating a platform of unprecedented tools for monitoring and control based on multimodal data, improving the robustness and accuracy of tasks such as state estimation, event classification, and decision-making. However, when the sensors in a system are spatially distributed and connected via wireless links, the fusion centre is prone to the reception of *out-of-order measurements*. This is a direct consequence of the random delays induced by, e.g., sensing and communication. If not addressed properly, the existence of out-of-order measurements affects how the system perceives the event chronology, having an impact on the task performance. Such an impact is especially critical in decision-making tasks, as different execution paths may be taken depending on how a sequence of events is perceived by the system. Therefore, resilient task completion requires preservation of event chronology at the fusion centre, ensuring that all observations will be processed in the order they were originally generated.

Inspired by the mechanisms that enable the human multi-sensory perception, the *TWI framework* [P24] proposes the establishment of timing constraints to process events, guaranteeing their correct temporal ordering. The essential concept behind this framework consists of defining a finite time window to integrate physical and digital inputs in a device. Accordingly, all inputs integrated during the same TWI are treated as simultaneous events, while inputs integrated over successive TWIs are considered causally related events. With that, the chronology of sensing events can be preserved even in the presence of random and dynamic delays, depending on setting the proper TWI duration. Then, the main challenge becomes optimizing the TWI duration to meet the desired degrees of simultaneity and causality preservation—which can be evaluated by the metrics introduced in [6GGOALS-D22]—while maintaining a low event throughput loss.

In cyber-physical systems with distributed sensors, mechanisms to preserve the temporal causality of sensing data are paramount when the system behaviour depends on sequences of events. For instance, in decision-making, the temporal causality reflects the chronological order in which events are perceived by the system, serving as pivotal point for computing assertive interventions. As a second example, in learning, datasets composed of distributed observations are subject to random delays that lead to a disordered perception of the event sequence. In this case, methods to preserve temporal causality such as the TWIs allow the construction of reliable datasets for training AI models. Given the importance of temporal consistency of events in these scenarios, this section investigates the application of the TWI framework to preserve the chronology of sensing events in multi-sensory systems with wireless links.

4.2 System model and problem statement

The scenario depicted in Figure 4-1 is considered, where an application hosted at the Base Station (BS) monitors a physical process based on status updates sent via wireless transmission by I distributed sensors. The sensors produce and transmit updates after every event occurrence in the physical process. To preserve the event chronology, the application must “perceive” all the updates resulting from the same physical event as simultaneous, processing them altogether. Then, the BS must ensure that such updates will be delivered concurrently to the application. To do so, the BS stores the updates in a buffer and delivers them to the application under two situations: 1) when all status updates have been successfully received and stored in

the buffer, or 2) when W seconds have passed after the reception and storage of the first update. Therefore, W is the maximum time window at which the application will perceive the updates as simultaneous, being the duration of the application's TWI.

Figure 4-1 System to monitor a physical process from event-driven status updates produced by distributed sensors.

In the proposed system, the chronology preservation of the status updates can be evaluated by investigating the relationship between the TWI duration W and the time interval for the BS to receive the status updates resulting from the same physical event. To characterize this time interval, the sensing and communication processes shown in Figure 4-2 are considered. In the sensing process, each sensor observes the physical signals generated by the monitored process, producing a data packet containing the status update after a random computation delay. Then, in the communication process, each sensor transmits the produced status update following a protocol comprised of 1) a random-access scheduling request step, followed by 2) a packet transmission scheduled by the BS. As the wireless channel presents dynamic and unpredictable behaviour, a packet reception might end after a random number of scheduling requests and packet transmission attempts, resulting in a random communication delay. Further details on the sensing and communications processes are described in [ISS+25].

Figure 4-2 Timing diagram illustrating a physical process event, the generation and transmission of status updates related to that event by two sensors, and the delivery of updates to the application based on the TWI framework.

By modelling the random timing components of the sensing and communication processes of Figure 4-2, it is possible to calculate the statistical distribution of the time interval between the reception at the BS of the first (fastest) and last (slowest) status updates, namely the Packet Delay Variation (PDV). Knowing the distribution of the PDV, the chronology preservation given by a TWI duration W is evaluated by the Probability of Simultaneity Violation (PSV), which refers to the event of having status updates related to the same physical event delivered to the application in different TWIs. This work aims to develop statistical models for the timing components and the PDV, then design the TWI duration to obtain a target PSV based on the characteristics of the physical, sensing, and communication processes.

4.3 Proposed methodology and solution

To characterize the statistical model of the PDV, it is first necessary to develop models for the individual timing components associated with physical propagation, computation, and communication. The developed models are organized in Table 4-1 and are combined to compute the time at which the status update of the sensor i will arrive at the BS, namely, the packet arrival time

$$t_i^{PA} = \left\lceil \frac{t_i^{EA} + C_i}{T_f} \right\rceil T_f + T_i^{SR} + T_i^{PT},$$

where T_f denotes the duration of a single communication frame. These models connect the properties of the physical process, and the computation and communication parameters to the delays experienced by the BS in the reception of status updates.

From the packet arrival time, the PDV is computed by the difference between the arrival time of the packets containing the first and the last received status updates,

$$\Delta = \max_{i \in I'} \{t_i^{PA}\} - \min_{i \in I'} \{t_i^{PA}\},$$

where I' is the subset of sensors that have not dropped their packets due to successive communication errors. The PDV distribution can be derived using order statistics and the statistical models in Table 4-1. However, to provide a simple analytical interpretation of the system behaviour, approximations for the PDV distribution in a system with 2 sensors are derived. The approximations are essential to facilitate a tractable design of the TWI.

Table 4-1 Timing components and developed statistical models.

Component	Timing components	Statistical model
Physical propagation	Event action time (t_i^{EA})	Linear distribution parameterized by the propagation velocity (v) and the maximum distance from the sensors to the physical process (D_{max})
Computation	Computation delay (C_i)	Uniform distribution parameterized by the minimum (C_{min}) and maximum (C_{max}) computation delays
Communication	Scheduling request delay (T_i^{SR}) Packet transmission delay (T_i^{PT})	Geometric distribution parameterized by the probability of the BS failing to detect a scheduling request (ζ_i) and a transmitted packet (ϵ_i), respectively

The approximations derived for the PDV distribution are organized in Table 4-2. The first approximation applies to scenarios where the computation delay governs the PDV, while the second one is suited to scenarios where the propagation delay dominates the PDV. The derivations of the Probability Distribution Functions (PDFs) and Cumulative Distribution Functions (CDFs) are detailed in Lemmas 1 and 2 of [ISS+25]. Specifically, the CDFs represent the probability that the PDV is below a given threshold, which is essential for verifying if the status updates will reach the BS in time for concurrent delivery toward the application, preserving the event chronology. For this reason, the CDFs of the PDV will be employed to propose a TWI design aiming to achieve a target PSV.

Design of the TWI

To design the TWI, it is first necessary to derive the PSV. In the 2-sensor scenario, the simultaneity violation event occurs if, upon the reception of one packet containing a status update, the packet containing the other one is dropped by its sensor due to successive communication

errors, or it arrives at the BS after the TWI duration W . Let L_2 denotes the packet drop event for the latter sensor, with probability given by the packet drop rate ρ_2 . Then, the PSV is

$$Pr\{L_2 \cup \Delta > W\} = 1 - (1 - \rho_2)Pr\{\Delta < W\}.$$

The term $Pr\{\Delta < W\}$ is the CDF of the PDV, which can be approximated by the expressions in Table 4-2. By replacing the CDF with the first approximation, the PSV when the computation delay governs the PDV is obtained,

$$\sigma_{Comp.} = 1 - (1 - \rho_2)F_{\Delta_{Comp.}}(W).$$

Then, by replacing the CDF with the second approximation, the PSV when the propagation delay dominates the PDV is obtained,

$$\sigma_{Prop.} = 1 - (1 - \rho_2)F_{\Delta_{Prop.}}(W).$$

The derived approximations describe the PSV dependence on the TWI duration, the properties of the physical process, and the computation and communication parameters. By inverting the expressions, the TWI duration can be designed to satisfy a target PSV.

Table 4-2 Approximations for the PDV distribution.

PDF	CDF
<i>Scenario 1: Computation delay governs the PDV</i>	
$f_{\Delta_{Comp.}}(t) = \frac{2(C_{max} - C_{min} - t)}{(C_{max} - C_{min})^2}, t \in [0, C_{max} - C_{min}]$	$F_{\Delta_{Comp.}}(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{2(C_{max} - C_{min})t - t^2}{(C_{max} - C_{min})^2}, t \in [0, C_{max} - C_{min}] \\ 1, t > C_{max} - C_{min} \end{cases}$
<i>Scenario 2: Propagation delay governs the PDV</i>	
$f_{\Delta_{Prop.}}(t) = \frac{2v^4}{3D_{max}^4} \left(2t^3 - \frac{6D_{max}^2}{v^2}t + \frac{4D_{max}^3}{v^3} \right), t \in \left[0, \frac{D_{max}}{v} \right]$	$F_{\Delta_{Prop.}}(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{2v^4}{3D_{max}^4} \left(\frac{1}{2}t^4 - \frac{3D_{max}^2}{v^2}t^2 + \frac{4D_{max}^3}{v^3}t \right), t \in \left[0, \frac{D_{max}}{v} \right] \\ 1, t > \frac{D_{max}}{v} \end{cases}$

4.4 Results

Numerical simulations were carried out to analyse the performance of the monitoring system. Figure 4-3 depicts the PSV calculated by the approximations and obtained in the numerical experiments for the two scenarios. At first glance, it can be seen that the approximations accurately model the PSV dependence on the TWI duration, being powerful tools to design W aiming to achieve a certain degree of event chronology preservation. Ultimately, the PSV is lower bounded by the packet drop rate, meaning that a full optimization of the system must account not only for the TWI duration but also for the communication parameters.

Further, Figure 4-4 shows the TWI computed by the approximations and the resulting latency in the two scenarios. Specifically, the latency denotes the time interval from the event occurrence at the physical process to the delivery of the produced status updates to the application within the first available TWI. It can be noticed that the average latency can be lower than the TWI duration, since the random delays can make all status updates arrive less than W seconds. On the other hand, in several cases, the latency is higher than the TWI due to the high computation or propagation delay for the reception of the first status update, which triggers the start of a new TWI. Therefore, the latency is not completely driven by the buffering time defined by the TWI duration but is also affected by the sensing and computation processes.

Figure 4-3 PSV calculated by the approximations and in numerical experiments for the scenarios where the computation delay governs the PDV (right) and the propagation delay governs the PDV (left).

Figure 4-4 TWI computed by the approximations and resulting latency for the scenarios where the computation delay governs the PDV (top) and the propagation delay governs the PDV (bottom).

4.5 Conclusions

This section investigated the problem of preserving the chronology of sensing events in multi-sensory systems with wireless links. Initially, a statistical model was introduced to describe the delays induced by the propagation of the physical signals generated by the monitored process, the computation delay involved in the sensing task, and the communication delay to convey the updates to the BS. Then, advancing the characterization of the metrics introduced in [6GGOALS-D22], this model was applied to derive the PSV depending on the TWI duration, the properties of the physical process, and the sensing and communication parameters. Finally, two analytical approximations for the PSV were derived to design the TWI duration to achieve a certain degree of event chronology preservation. Numerical results revealed the approximations' high accuracy and showed that the latency for event perception by the application is not driven totally by the TWI duration. Future works will generalize the analysis to scenarios with more than 2 sensors, capitalizing on the findings for monitoring cyber-physical systems.

5 Causally-Structured Image Semantic Communications with GenAI

5.1 Context and Motivation

The surge in visual data presents unique challenges to communication systems, primarily due to the richness of the content and the inherent ambiguity of images. Addressing these challenges is crucial for advancing Image Semantic Communication (ISC) technologies, which hold the potential to revolutionize user experience and dramatically improve overall efficiency.

Despite the promising advancements in Deep Joint Source-Channel Coding (JSCC)-based schemes, several significant limitations persist, hindering their widespread adoption, trustworthiness, and effectiveness [6GGOALS-D22] [6GGOALS-D42]. These challenges include: i) lack of interpretability in semantic representations, as the extracted semantics are represented as opaque feature vectors, impeding algorithm optimization and human understanding; ii) operability issues in model training, where the joint training and simultaneous updating requirements for transmitter and receiver models complicate deployment, particularly for multi-downstream tasks; iii) compatibility problems in signal transmission, where the assumption of direct complex-valued signal transmission through channels often conflicts with current communication systems and hardware architectures; and iv) inefficiencies in multi-rate and multi-task scenarios, where current techniques fail to maximize transmission efficiency because of overlooking the semantics of source content.

In this work, we propose a novel causality-aware trustworthy ISC framework designed to enhance explainability, controllability, and operability [WYC+25]. Our framework features an image semantic encoder at the transmitter, which leverages pre-trained foundation models to convert images into explainable semantics through text extraction and segmentation mapping. At the receiver end, we employ cutting-edge Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) to perform multiple downstream inference tasks, including image caption generation, image segmentation, and image reconstruction. The transmitter utilizes pre-trained models which has been trained with massive amounts of data and good generalization capabilities on diverse tasks, reducing task-specific adjustments, while the receiver can independently update and train using pre-generated semantic data. Furthermore, we introduced a policy controller with causal reasoning, in which each scheduling decision for the next semantic packet is guided by the receiver feedback that captures the historical cause-and-effect links between delivered semantics and task performance. This feedback forms a closed-loop cycle, whereby semantic inputs and downstream outcomes iteratively inform one another, embedding causal inference directly into the transmission process.

5.2 System model and problem statement

Our proposed unified end-to-end trustworthy ISC framework, illustrated in Figure 5-1, harnesses GenAI for multitask processing. The trustworthiness of this framework is underpinned by its explainability and controllability, which are ensured through two key aspects. Firstly, we employ explainable semantics as image semantic carriers, including image semantic text and image semantic segmentation maps. Secondly, the multi-rate transmission control is dynamically determined by both the received explainable semantic content and the specific task requirements at the receiver. This approach enables a flexible communication system adaptive to varying needs. A detailed description of the main components will be given in the below.

The framework incorporates an image semantic encoder at the transmitter. This encoder, built upon a pre-trained foundation model, generates explainable semantics in discrete representation. At the receiver end, we implement an Explainable Semantics-based Image Reconstruction Module (ES-IRM). This module is designed to facilitate high quality image reconstruction using the transmitted explainable semantics. Additionally, the framework also includes encoder and

modulation module for transmitting explainable semantics through digital communication systems over physical channels. Similarly, semantics are recovered through decode and demodulation module at the receiver.

Figure 5-1 An end-to-end trustworthy ISC framework with causality reasoning-based semantic controller [WYC+25]

1) Image Semantic Encoder: The encoder is designed to transform images into explainable semantics that facilitate downstream inference tasks. This encoder extracts two primary types of semantics: image semantic text (IS-text) and multi-level image semantic segmentation. As illustrated in Figure 5-2, the latter encompasses three distinct levels of segmentation maps: Annotated Segmentation Map (A-seg), which provides a semantic segmentation map with object labels and instance boxes; Boundary-aware Segmentation Map (B-seg), offering a comprehensive segmentation map with fine contours based on the segment anything model; and S-img, comprising sub-images of each object identified in A-seg, obtained through Region of Interest (ROI)-based masking operations on the original image. T_N and I_N denote the generated text and image feature vector, Z_N denotes the additional noise for generative model training, NER stands for Named Entity Recognition, and DFS-block stands for Deep text-image-segmentation Fusion Block. We employ specific pre-trained models for extracting different types of semantics from images. The CoCa model is used for extracting semantic text, while the YOLOv8 model and the FastSAM model are used for semantic segmentation [ZCS+23]. More specifically, YOLOv8 extracts segmentation maps for A-seg, whereas FastSAM handles segmentation for B-seg. Importantly, all these semantic representations are generated in discrete data formats, ensuring seamless transmission over physical channels using modern digital communication systems. This multi-faceted approach to semantic extraction not only enhances the richness of the transmitted information but also maintains compatibility with existing communication systems.

2) ES-IRM: This module at the receiver leverages the Generative Adversarial contrastive Language-Image Pre-training (GALIP) model, offering superior generation speed and computational efficiency compared to diffusion and autoregressive models. The ES-IRM's core architecture, illustrated in Figure 5-2, harnesses the powerful image-text pairing capability of the Contrastive Language-Image Pre-training (CLIP) model. It comprises a CLIP text encoder with its corresponding generator and a CLIP image encoder (CLIP-ViT) paired with its discriminator.

The process begins with the CLIP text encoder producing a text feature vector T_N , which, concatenated with a random noise vector Z_N , serves as input to the generator network. Concurrently, the CLIP-ViT generates an image feature vector I_N . The discriminator then utilizes both I_N and T_N to perform accurate similarity reasoning, validating the correspondence between the input image and text features. This mechanism guides the generator in producing text-consistent reconstructed images, ensuring a high-fidelity output that aligns with the transmitted semantic information. The generator network in our ES-IRM employs a sophisticated architecture comprising a feature map module and multiple Deep Fusion of text/image Segmentation (DFS) blocks designed to enhance image reconstruction fidelity. Initially, the feature map module transforms the concatenated text feature vector and noise vector into an intermediate feature map. The DFS blocks, central to our approach, then take on the crucial task of image reconstruction based on this intermediate representation. These blocks fuse the text feature vector and received image segmentation maps into the reconstruction process, utilizing an affine layer [TTW+22] and a spatially adaptive normalization (SPADE) layer, respectively. This novel DFS-Block design significantly mitigates structure-level disparities between the generated and original images, ensuring a high degree of visual and semantic coherence. Consequently, our ES-IRM demonstrates remarkable capability in reconstructing high-quality images that are visually similar and semantically close to the origin image.

Figure 5-2 Details of key components in the trustworthy ISC framework

5.3 Proposed methodology and solution

We now introduce our proposed controllability design in semantic-level multi-rate transmission. Our proposed approach achieves semantic-aware multi-rate transmission through three key components: a policy controller at the transmitter, a correlation analysis module at the receiver, and a shared vector database. This system facilitates adaptive and controllable data transmission, dynamically responding to both the semantic content of the communicated information and the specific requirements of the receiver’s task.

1) Correlation Analysis Module: The receiver employs a correlation analysis module to evaluate the relevance of received semantics to the task at hand. This process begins with both the task description and image semantic texts being processed through a Named Entity Recognition (NER) module to extract significant entity words. These extracted words are then converted into vector representations using a pre-trained word embedding model. The module subsequently calculates the cosine similarity among the vectorized task descriptions, image semantic texts, and the vector database.

2) Policy Controller: The policy controller at the transmitter strategically selects appropriate semantics for transmission based on feedback from the receiver regarding the type and status of downstream tasks. Initially, the image semantic text is sent due to its low communication cost compared to the entire image. The controller then iteratively selects which sub-semantics to transmit based on ongoing feedback until the task is reported as completed.

3) Vector Database: The transmitter and receiver share a vector database containing word embeddings for all classes extracted by the image semantic encoder in A-seg. These embeddings, generated using models like Word2Vec, enable efficient computation of similarity between downstream tasks and image semantic texts. The use of word embeddings is beneficial for accurately handling synonyms and semantic relationships through similarity calculations in the vector space.

5.4 Results

To evaluate the performance of the proposed framework, we use the common objects in context (CoCo) dataset [LMB+14]. We choose 50 images per category, resulting in a total of 4,000 test images. This selection method ensures that each category appears in approximately 400 images, providing a balanced representation across the dataset. For generating image captions task, the Bilingual Evaluation Understudy (BLEU) score is used to primarily measure the similarity between two sentences [LLL+24]. For the image reconstruction task, three commonly used performance metrics are employed: Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) to indicate the pixel-level consistency of the reconstructed image, Learned Perceptual Image Patch Similarity (LPIPS) to measure the content consistency of the reconstructed image, and Fréchet Inception Distance (FID) to assess the diversity and distribution consistency between the reconstructed and original image sets.

Table 5-1 Image reconstruction performance

Scheme	PSNR	LPIPS	FID
JPEG-q1	20.779	0.432	159.063
SPADE	11.507	0.534	63.601
GALIP	9.406	0.597	39.846
ES-IRM-A (Proposal)	9.181	0.552	55.398
ES-IRM-B (Proposal)	10.375	0.403	34.509

Our proposed framework, particularly the ES-IRM-B variant, demonstrates superior performance in image reconstruction tasks, as evidenced by Table 5-1. ES-IRM-B achieves the best results in semantic-awareness metrics, specifically LPIPS and FID scores, where lower values indicate closer semantic similarity to the original image. Figure 5-3 visually confirms this superiority, showing ES-IRM-B's ability to closely replicate original image content, including specific details like a purple bus, a laptop, and buildings. In contrast, alternative methods exhibit significant limitations: JPEG-q1 suffers from severe color distortion and blocky artifacts due to extreme compression; SPADE struggles with complete object depiction (e.g., a purple bus), relying solely on segmentation maps; GALIP, using only semantic text, produces images drastically different from the originals (e.g., the reconstruction images of a baseball player swinging a bat and a laptop); and ES-IRM-A, while an improvement, lacks sufficient detail in some cases (e.g.,

a laptop). Overall, the proposed framework consistently generates more comprehensive and detailed reconstructions at comparable compression ratios, making it a promising solution for efficient image transmission and reconstruction.

Figure 5-3 Visualization of image reconstruction quality for various schemes.

We also evaluate the proposed method under a single-user multi-task scenario, in which we simulate a scenario where a user must complete a diverse set of 480 tasks: 160 each for image captioning, segmentation, and reconstruction. These tasks are presented in random order to mimic real-world variability. We ensure task diversity by involving each category target in two distinct tasks. To create a comprehensive test dataset, we utilize Python’s COCO API library functions to filter and select images from the COCO dataset. Specifically, we choose 50 images per category, resulting in a total of 4,000 test images. This selection method ensures that each category appears in approximately 400 images, providing a balanced representation across the dataset. We compare our proposed framework with three baseline schemes. The digital scheme combines the JPEG algorithm with traditional digital communication methods. As it lacks knowledge of specific downstream tasks, it uses a standard image compression rate (e.g., JPEG-q30) to ensure adequate quality for various potential tasks. The digital with knowledge scheme, while similar, leverages task awareness to optimize resource usage. It employs JPEG-q25 compression for image captioning while maintaining the digital scheme’s approach for other tasks. Lastly, the ISC with knowledge scheme, grounded in explainable semantics and task awareness, selectively transmits specific types of sub-semantics tailored to each task.

Table 5-2 illustrates the average data transmission requirements for each communication scheme. The digital scheme, employing JPEG compression at q30 for all tasks, requires 5,761.12 bytes per image. The digital with knowledge scheme reduces this for image caption tasks by using a lower compression rate. Our proposed framework and the ISC with knowledge scheme demonstrate superior efficiency for image caption tasks, requiring only 200 bytes of image semantic text. For image segmentation, leveraging the fact that each category appears in only 400 out of 4,000 test images, our correlation analysis module eliminates unnecessary

data transmission for irrelevant images. Consequently, the average data required per image segmentation task is merely 395.21 bytes, with only 10% of tasks needing both semantic text and A-seg maps. Similarly, an average of only 465.03 bytes is needed to complete an image reconstruction task. These results underscore the significant advantages of our proposed framework in multitask scenarios, showcasing its ability to efficiently allocate communication resources based on specific task requirements and image content relevance.

Table 5-2 The average amount of communication data required to complete multiple tasks in multiple schemes (unit: bytes)

Scheme	Image caption task	Image segmentation task	Image reconstruction task
Digital scheme	5761.12	5761.12	5761.12
Digital with knowledge scheme	4684.57	5761.12	5761.12
ISC with knowledge	200	1952.09	2850.29
(Ours) Semantic-level multi-rate ISC	200	395.21	465.03

5.5 Conclusion

In this work, we have investigated a trustworthy image semantic communication framework based on a decoupled transceiver model, utilizing explainable and system-compatible semantics. The framework employs image semantic text and image semantic segmentation maps as carriers for image semantics. Experimental results demonstrate that the proposed framework supports tasks such as image captioning, image semantic segmentation, and image reconstruction, outperforming traditional image compression and digital communication methods across all three tasks. Additionally, we have proposed a semantic-level multi-rate communication scheme. The experimental results show that it can achieve a 90% reduction in the communication data volume required for semantic image communication.

6 Causal Abstraction Learning based on the Semantic Embedding Principle

6.1 Context and motivation

Causal reasoning is key to semantic and goal-oriented communication, where meaningful information is conveyed not merely as raw data but as representations optimized for specific inference tasks and decision-making goals [TSX23, TS24, WB25]. Indeed, the extraction of causal representations from raw data enables the creation of causally-invariant semantic representations, thus making AI-native communication networks trustworthy, robust to distributional shifts, and enabling the three levels of Pearl’s causal hierarchy—observation (level 1), intervention (level 2), and counterfactual reasoning (level 3)—going beyond correlation.

Structural Causal Models (SCMs, [P09]) are the gold standard for representing cause-effect relationships in complex systems, and a powerful tool for causal semantic communication. Existing approaches [TSX23, TS24, WB25] implicitly assume a single, fixed scale (or resolution) for causal relations. However, such a scale is not known in advance. Moreover, real-world applications often require integrating causal knowledge across multiple levels of resolution - for example, linking molecular interactions to organism-level behaviour, or connecting fine-grained brain activity to large-scale lobar dynamics. An open challenge, therefore, is to endow AI-native communication systems with the ability to perform causal reasoning at varying resolutions and to select the most suitable scale for each communication task.

Towards our goal, the Causal Abstraction (CA) framework [BH19, R20] offers a rigorous formalism for relating low- and high-level SCMs, but the necessary abstraction maps are typically unknown and must be learned from data [ZDA+23]. Existing CA-learning methods typically rely

on restrictive assumptions. Specifically, (i) knowledge of the underlying SCMs [ZDA+23, FZB+24, MMB24], (ii) availability of interventional data [ZDA+23, FZB+24], and (iii) alignment of samples across SCMs [MMB24]. These assumptions limit existing methods' applicability in domains where interventions are infeasible and jointly sampled data are unavailable. Yet in many settings, a modest amount of prior structural information is naturally available. For example, neuroscientists know how ROIs map onto anatomical lobes even when the detailed causal mechanisms within each region remain unknown.

Motivated by these challenges, this work [DZF+25] introduces the Semantic Embedding Principle (SEP), which posits that the high-level causal knowledge lies within a subspace of the low-level one, guaranteeing that embedding followed by abstraction faithfully reconstructs high-level causal knowledge. SEP inherently aligns with semantic and goal-oriented communication, providing a principled way for preserving the interventionally consistent semantic representations in communication systems. Hence, in an AI-native communication system, coarse-grained semantics live in a subspace of the fine-grained ones, and CA mappings enable transitions from one scale to another. Thanks to interventional consistency, these transitions remain valid under interventions, thus no adjustment of the CA mappings is required.

Figure 6-1 Pictorial representation of SEP for linear CA.

As an example, Figure 6-1 depicts SEP for the case of linear CA between two causal models. A linear map V belonging to the Stiefel manifold embeds a high-level causal knowledge χ^h into a low-level one, viz. χ^ℓ , identifying an embedded causal knowledge $\varphi_{\#}^{V^T}(\chi^h)$. Then, a linear CA V^T abstracts $\varphi_{\#}^{V^T}(\chi^h)$, yielding a causal knowledge identical to χ^h . Notice that the arrow Id_{χ^h} underlines that commutativity holds only in one direction, that is, SEP does not imply $\varphi_{\#}^{V^T \circ V}(\chi^\ell) = \chi^\ell$. By casting SCMs and their abstractions in a category-theoretic framework guided by SEP [DZF+25], we formulate a general learning problem that operates solely on the semantic level, thus relaxing the restrictive assumptions and paving the way for CA learning in realistic scenarios, such as goal-oriented communication systems.

6.2 System model and problem formulation

Consider low- and high-level SCMs, viz. M^ℓ and M^h . The former involves ℓ causal variables, the latter h , with $\ell > h$. Our problem formulation builds upon three key ingredients.

First, we assume that the data generated by a constructive α -abstraction [R20] adheres to SEP. This principle requires that the CA map - denoted by α_x - admits a right-inverse measurable map. Constructivity means that all low-level causal variables are relevant for CA. The SEP implies that going from the high-level model M^h to the low-level model M^ℓ and then abstracting back to M^h allows for perfect reconstruction.

Second, we work at the distributional (semantic) level of the SCMs. Thus, we consider as an input the observational probability measures of M^ℓ and M^h , viz. χ^ℓ and χ^h , respectively. Further, we assume that only partial prior knowledge of the CA structure - denoted by m_x - is available, which is reasonable in different application settings.

Third, to learn a CA, we look for a distance function quantifying the misalignment between the probability measures χ^ℓ and χ^h , given α_x . Since the probability measures belong to spaces of different dimensionality, we compute the misalignment through an embedding as $D(\chi^h, \varphi_{\#}^{\alpha_x}(\chi^\ell))$ [DZF+25], where D is an information-theoretic metric (e.g., p -Wasserstein) or ϕ -divergence (e.g., Kullback-Leibler), and $\varphi_{\#}^{\alpha_x}(\chi^\ell)$ is the pushforward measure entailed by the CA α_x . Below is the general learning problem.

Problem 1. (SEP-based CA learning)

Input: (i) probability measures χ^ℓ and χ^h ; (ii) prior information about m_x , and (iii) a distance function $D(\chi^h, \varphi_{\#}^{\alpha_x}(\chi^\ell))$.

Goal: learn a measurable map α_x^* such that (i) $D(\chi^h, \varphi_{\#}^{\alpha_x^*}(\chi^\ell))$ vanishes, (ii) it agrees with SEP, and (iii) it agrees with the prior information about m_x .

As an application, we consider Problem 1 in case of:

Linear and constructive CA [MMB24]. In this setting α_x can be represented as an $h \times \ell$ real matrix, viz. V^T . To comply with SEP, the transpose V must belong to the Stiefel manifold, that is, $V^T V = I_h$, where I_h is the identity matrix of size $h \times h$;

Gaussian measures. Specifically, $\chi^\ell = N(0, \Sigma^\ell)$ and $\chi^h = N(0, \Sigma^h)$;

KL divergence. In detail,

$$D_{KL}(\chi^h, \varphi_{\#}^V(\chi^\ell)) = \text{Tr}\{(V^T \Sigma^\ell V)^{-1} \Sigma^h\} + \log \det V^T \Sigma^\ell V + \text{const.}$$

We investigate two approaches for injecting the prior information about m_x , encoded in the matrix of prior knowledge $B \in \{0,1\}^{\ell \times h}$, into our problem. These formulations translate into non-smooth unconstrained and smooth constrained Riemannian learning problems [DZF+25]. In the former, we add to the (smooth) $D_{KL}(\chi^h, \varphi_{\#}^V(\chi^\ell))$ a non-smooth term $h(V)$ penalizing the entries of V which correspond to the null entries in B . In the latter, we directly use B as a masking matrix within $D_{KL}(\chi^h, \varphi_{\#}^V(\chi^\ell))$. Notably, the latter formulation is particularly convenient as it enables us to jointly optimize for V and its support S , guaranteeing constructivity by design.

6.3 Proposed methodology and solution

Non-smooth unconstrained learning problem. We propose two algorithms: *LinSEPAL-ADMM* and *LinSEPAL-PG*, where *LinSEPAL* stands for **L**inear **S**emantic **E**mbedding **P**rinciple **A**bstraction **L**earner.

LinSEPAL-ADMM builds upon the *manifold alternating direction method of multipliers* (MADMM, [KGB16]) optimization paradigm. MADMM appeals to our setting given the objective function separating into smooth and non-smooth terms. To derive the *LinSEPAL-ADMM* iterative algorithm, we proceed as follows. First, the non-smooth term $h(V)$ is associated with a splitting variable Y to be optimized over $\mathbb{R}^{\ell \times h}$. *LinSEPAL-ADMM* proceeds by iteratively minimizing the augmented Lagrangian with respect to the primal variables V and Y , while maximizing w.r.t. the scaled dual variable. Specifically, *LinSEPAL-ADMM* solves the subproblem for V through standard techniques for smooth optimization on the Stiefel manifold [DZF+25]. Next, *LinSEPAL-ADMM* updates Y in closed form through the element-wise soft-thresholding operator. Finally, the scaled dual variable is updated by adding the primal residual evaluated at the current solution. The stopping criteria for *LinSEPAL-ADMM* are established according to primal and dual feasibility optimality conditions [BPC+11].

LinSEPAL-PG builds upon the *manifold proximal gradient* (ManPG, [CMM+20]) optimization paradigm. *LinSEPAL-PG* is an iterative algorithm alternating two updates. The first update is the proximal mapping providing a proximal gradient direction G^k onto the tangent space to the Stiefel manifold, using the first-order approximation of the objective around the k -th estimate. The second is the update for V^{k+1} , which exploits the canonical retraction technique for projecting back $V^k + G^k$, from the tangent space to the manifold. The optimization stops either when a maximum number of iterations is reached, or when D_{KL} is below a threshold $\tau \approx 0$. *LinSEPAL-PG* inherits the global convergence of the ManPG framework, established in [CMM+20].

Smooth constrained learning problem. We propose the CLinSEPAL method for solving this learning problem, where the C stands for **Constructive**. Indeed, CLinSEPAL is the only method guaranteeing a constructive CA. CLinSEPAL jointly optimizes S and V , both being components of the linear CA, viz. $B \circ S \circ V$, where B is the prior as above. CLinSEPAL results in an iterative procedure that combines three optimization frameworks:

- *Splitting orthogonality constraints* (SOC, [LO14]) for isolating the Riemannian part via the usage of suitable splitting variables;
- *Alternating direction method of multipliers* (ADMM, [BPC+11]) for isolating the nonconvexity into different subproblems;
- *Successive convex approximations* (SCA, [NPS+14]) to solve the nonconvex subproblems.

6.4 Results

In our empirical assessment, given the values for (ℓ, h) , we generate the synthetic data by randomly sampling Σ^ℓ and a ground truth V^* of size $\ell \times h$ belonging to the Stiefel manifold. Then, we set $\Sigma^h = V^{*\top} \Sigma^\ell V^*$. We tested *LinSEPAL-ADMM*, *LinSEPAL-PG*, and CLinSEPAL with different degrees of prior structural knowledge, from full (fp) to partial (pp). The monitored metrics are: (i) constructiveness (in $[0,1]$, the higher the better); (ii) KL divergence for evaluating the alignment between $\varphi_{\#}^{\hat{V}}(\chi^\ell)$ and χ^h (the lower the better); (iii) the Frobenius distance between the absolute value of the learned \hat{V} and that of the ground truth V^* (the lower the better), normalized by V^* to make the settings comparable; (iv) the F1 score computed using the support of the learned CAs and that of V^* to evaluate structural interventional consistency (in $[0,1]$, the higher the better). It is useful to monitor the latter metric even in the fp case since *LinSEPAL-ADMM* and *LinSEPAL-PG*, unlike CLinSEPAL, do not guarantee CA constructiveness and thus that the prior is met.

In the fp case, we investigate three different settings $(\ell, h) \in \{(12,2), (12,4), (12,6)\}$, corresponding to the cases of *high*, *medium-high*, and *medium* coarse-graining. The latter values are realistic in application domains such as neuroscience [DZF+25]. We do not consider the case where $h > \ell/2$ since the abstraction for $h - \ell/2$ nodes of the low-level model would be fully specified

due to the availability of full prior knowledge. For each setting, we instantiate $T = 30$ ground truth abstractions V^* , and for each simulation $t \in [T]$ we run all the methods $R = 50$ times, with different initializations. Then, for each t and method, we retain the \hat{V} minimizing the objective.

Figure 6-2 depicts the results. All methods return constructive CAs (top left); minimize the misalignment (top right); return CAs respecting the prior knowledge (bottom right) and close to the ground truth in absolute terms for the second and third setting (bottom left). The greater Frobenius distance in the first setting is driven by the increasing dimension of the kernel of the KL. Overall, CLinSEPAL and LinSEPAL-ADMM outperform LinSEPAL-PG.

Figure 6-2 Synthetic full prior results for three different settings $(\ell, h) \in \{(12, 2), (12, 4), (12, 6)\}$, corresponding to the cases of *high*, *medium-high*, and *medium coarse-graining*.

In the *pp case*, we consider the setting $(\ell, h) = (4, 2)$ corresponding to medium coarse-graining and simulate partial prior knowledge by removing the prior for 25%, 50%, and 70% of the variables. For each setting, we instantiate $T = 30$ ground truth abstractions V^* , and for each simulation $t \in [T]$ we run all the methods $R = 30$ times, with different initializations.

Figure 6-3 shows the results. CLinSEPAL is the only method providing constructive CAs in each setting (top left). We decided to consider methods performing under a threshold of 90% to be unreliable in returning constructive CAs and not to report their remaining metrics. Looking at the latter metrics, in the first setting all the methods perform well. In the second, LinSEPAL-PG fails, while CLinSEPAL and LinSEPAL-ADMM still do well. Finally, in the third setting only CLinSEPAL succeeds. Overall, CLinSEPAL outperforms the rest of the methods.

Figure 6-3 Synthetic partial prior results with $(\ell, h) = (4, 2)$ corresponding to medium coarse-graining.

6.5 Conclusions

We addressed the challenge of CA learning in realistic scenarios [DZF+25], abandoning restrictive assumptions discussed in *Context and motivation* that limit the applicability of existing methods. We proposed an alternative category-theoretic framework for SCM and CA, and introduced the *semantic embedding principle* to learn CAs that meaningfully preserve information. SEP inherently aligns with semantic and goal-oriented communication, paving the way for integrating CAs into AI-native 6G networks for enabling causal reasoning at different levels of resolutions while preserving semantics and ensuring interventional consistency. We formulated a general CA learning problem grounded in SEP, under a mild assumption of partial prior knowledge about the structure of CA. For the linear CA setting, we showed how SEP links CA to the geometry of the Stiefel manifold; as an application, we tackled the important case of Gaussian measures, with the KL divergence as a measure of alignment between the low- and high-level SCMs. We pursued two different formulations. For the first, a non-smooth unconstrained Riemannian learning problem, we devised the LinSEPAL-ADMM and LinSEPAL-PG methods. For the second, a smooth constrained Riemannian learning problem ensuring the constructiveness of the CA, we developed CLinSEPAL. Our empirical assessment on synthetic data confirmed the effectiveness of our methods.

7 Conclusion

This deliverable presented a set of complementary approaches for enabling causal semantic communication across multiple system domains, including control, sensing, perception, and abstraction. The central objective has been to move beyond conventional data transmission, focusing instead on the identification, representation, and use of information that carries causal relevance to system goals.

Each of the four technical contributions illustrates a different aspect of this paradigm. Section 3 demonstrated how causal innovations can support state estimation in wireless control systems without requiring full channel knowledge. Section 4 addressed the preservation of causal structure in event streams through temporal integration. Section 5 showed how semantic communication for images can be made task-aware through feedback-driven selection of causally relevant content. Section 6 introduced causal abstraction learning to enable generalization and scalability in semantic representation. Together, these results establish a layered view of causal semantic processing—starting from low-level sensing and estimation, extending to multimodal perception, and culminating in high-level reasoning. They are unified by shared principles: prioritizing information that drives task outcomes, preserving causal structure, and designing representations that can generalize across systems and contexts.

Looking ahead, these foundations pave the way for designing future 6G systems that are not only communication-efficient, but also intelligent, interpretable, and aligned with the dynamics of real-world decision-making. Further integration across modalities and deeper exploration of causal mechanisms will be key directions in advancing the vision of causal semantic networks.

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